

MEDIA PARTICIPATION AND ITS IMPORTANCE

Ahmedov Azimjon Ilhomovich

the teacher of Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

Bahodirova Ozoda

the student of Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages,

311-group – English language and literature

Abstract: This article provides information about mass media as well as its benefits. Information is a means of managing a person, his actions, activities of public organizations, state authorities, and technical systems. Information communication forms the basis of training, education and formation of a person. Information is the only means of conveying the content of social and technical norms to a person, warning him about the future negative consequences of not following these norms.

Keywords: mass media, news industry, political progress, powerful impact, conflict, advantage.

УЧАСТИЕ СМИ И ЕГО ЗНАЧЕНИЕ

Ахмедов Азимжон Ильхомович

преподаватель Андижанского государственного института иностранных

языков

Комилова Озода

студентка Андижанского государственного института иностранных языков,

311-группа – английский язык и литература

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены сведения о средствах массовой информации, а также их преимущества. Информация – это средство управления человеком, его действиями, деятельностью общественных организаций, органов государственной власти, технических систем.

Информационная коммуникация составляет основу обучения, воспитания и формирования личности. Информация является единственным средством донесения до человека содержания социальных и технических норм, предупреждения его о будущих негативных последствиях несоблюдения этих норм.

Ключевые слова: средства массовой информации, новостная индустрия, политический прогресс, мощное воздействие, конфликт, преимущество.

"Mass media" is a deceptively simple term encompassing a countless array of institutions and individuals who differ in purpose, scope, method, and cultural context. Mass media include all forms of information communicated to large groups of people, from a handmade sign to an international news network. There is no standard for how large the audience needs to be before communication becomes "mass" communication. There are also no constraints on the type of information being presented. A car advertisement, a fake social media post coming from Russia, and a U.N. resolution are all examples of mass media.

Because "media" is such a broad term, it will be helpful in this discussion to focus on a limited definition. In general usage, the term has been taken to refer to only "the group of corporate entities, publishers, journalists, and others who constitute the communications industry and profession." This definition includes both the entertainment and news industries. Another common term, especially in talking about conflict, is "news media." News media include only the news industry. It is often used interchangeably with "the press" or the group of people who write and report the news.

In 2020, this definition of mass media is clearly too narrow. Social media including Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, Tumblr and the like allows anyone in the world to post pretty much anything they want--true or false with very little oversight or censorship. This has resulted in the widespread use of "bots" computers that generate millions of fake, almost always inflammatory, stories which they widely post on these social media apps, masquerading as real people,

even as known friends of real people. This is thought to significantly sway public opinion toward the extremes in the world , for example, making conservatives think that liberals are far worse than they really are, and making liberals think the opposite. The result is increasing polarization of both the electorate and our decision makers, making our political processes largely dysfunctional.

Mass communicated media saturated the industrialized world in 2005; this is true for the non-industrialized world, too, in 2020.) The television in the living room, the newspaper on the doorstep (not so much anymore!), the radio in the car, the computer and tablet, the fliers in the mailbox, and now most importantly, perhaps in 2020, the cell phone are just a few of the media channels daily delivering advertisements, news, opinion, music, and other forms of mass communication.

Because the media are so prevalent, they have an extremely powerful impact on how we view the world. Nearly everything we know about current events and politics comes from the media--it is only the most local and personal events that are experienced first-hand. Events in the larger community, the state, the country, and the rest of the world are experienced almost entirely through the media, be it a professional journalist or a "citizen journalist" posting on social media.

Not only do the media report the news, they create the news by deciding what to report. The "top story" of the day has to be picked from the millions of things that happened that particular day. After something is deemed newsworthy, there are decisions on how much time or space to give it, whom to interview, what pictures to use, and how to frame it. Often considered by editors, but seldom discussed, is how the biases and interests of management will impact these determinations. All of these decisions add up to the audience's view of the world, and those who influence the decisions influence the audience.

The news media thrive on conflict. The lead story for most news programs is typically the most recent and extreme crime or disaster. Conflict attracts viewers, listeners, and readers to the media; the greater the conflict the greater the audience, and large audiences are imperative to the financial success of media outlets.

Therefore, it is often in the media's interest to not only report conflict, but to play it up, making it seem more intense than it really is. Long-term, on-going conflict-resolution processes such as mediation are not dramatic and are often difficult to understand and report, especially since the proceedings are almost always closed to the media. Thus conflict resolution stories are easily pushed aside in favor of the most recent, the most colorful, and the most shocking aspects of a conflict. Groups that understand this dynamic can cater to it in order to gain media attention. Common criteria for terrorist attacks include timing them to coincide with significant dates, targeting elites, choosing sites with easy media access, and aiming for large numbers of casualties.[1] Protesters will hoist their placards and start chanting when the television cameras come into view. It is not unusual for camera crews or reporters to encourage demonstrators into these actions so they can return to their studios with exciting footage. The resulting media coverage can bestow status and even legitimacy on marginal opposition groups, so television coverage naturally becomes one of their planned strategies and top priorities. The "30-second sound bite" has become a familiar phrase in television and radio news and alert public figures strategize to use it to their advantage.

The media, to sum up, have enormous importance to conflict resolution because they are the primary and frequently only source of information regarding conflicts. If a situation doesn't make the news (now including social media), it simply does not exist for most people. When peaceful options such as negotiation and other collaborative problem-solving techniques are not covered, or their successes are not reported, they become invisible and are not likely to be considered or even understood as possible options in the management of a conflict.

REFERENCE :

1. Nozima Muratova, Nargis Qosimova, Gulnoza Alimova, A'zam Dadaxonov, Azizaxon Ilyosxonova, Sitora Xolmatova, Nigina Xakimova: Jurnalistika "Onlayn

- jurnalistika va mediada yangi trendlar” –T.: O’zbekiston, 2019. 135-b.
- 2.Nesterenko F.P., Irnazarov K.T., Mamatova Y.M. Lug‘at-ma’lumotnoma: jurnalistika, reklama, pablik rileyshnz. - T., Zar qalam, 2003. 48-b.
- 3.Принципы международной журналистики и международный обмен информацией. –М., 1999. С.5.
- 4.<http://xs.uz/uzkr/post/prezident-tabrigi-matbuot-va-ommavij-akhborot-vositalari-khodimlariga>
5. O’zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining matbuot va ommaviy axborot vositalari xodimlariga tabrigi. “Xalq so’zi”, 2018 yil 28-iyun

